

Open Life Science Publication database (OLSPub)

Strengthening the Biomedical Research
Community by Building a Resilient and
Sustainable Solution

A third-party funding proposal by
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Project Description – Project Proposals in the Area of Scientific Library Services and Information Systems (LIS)

LIS Funding Program or Call: Specialised Information Services for Research; Special Proposal

Open Life Science Publication Database (OLSPub): Strengthening the Biomedical Research Community by Building a Resilient and Sustainable Solution

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Project Description

1 State of the art and preliminary work

Reliable access to scientific literature and robust information infrastructures are fundamental to efficient workflows, rapid progress and the overall resilience of the research ecosystem. PubMed – as the world’s largest and most widely used bibliographic database in medicine and the life sciences – plays a critical role for researchers and practitioners alike. However, recent shifts in US policy priorities have raised concerns among scientists in the life sciences community **that access to the PubMed database could be restricted** or that its established quality standards could be degraded (Richter-Kuhlmann, Eva 2025). This proposal presents a case for developing an **alternative service that will guarantee resilient and unrestricted access to life sciences bibliographic data** for researchers and the general public. Given the urgency of the situation, this project will adopt a fully transparent communication strategy. Key elements include announcing this proposal prior to submission, hosting an information event and maintaining a dedicated project website¹. Furthermore, this proposal will be made publicly available from the start of the review process²

1.1 PubMed's role and systemic risks to research access

PubMed³ is a freely accessible database operated by the US National Library of Medicine (NLM). It has served the global research community for decades and **contains more than 38 million citations to scientific publications from biomedical and life sciences journals, books, reviews and clinical studies**. Subject areas covered by the database include medicine, nursing, dentistry, veterinary medicine, healthcare and other areas of life sciences.⁴

PubMed is primarily based on the MEDLINE database, which is also managed by the NLM. MEDLINE comprises references from over **5,200 biomedical and life sciences journals**. **The reference data in MEDLINE is annotated with Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms**, a comprehensive controlled vocabulary with a taxonomic structure, synonyms and subheadings that enables precise and effective database searches. While the NLM develops and maintains the English MeSH vocabulary, international teams translate these terms into other languages, such as the German translation team at ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Science.

Beyond MEDLINE, PubMed incorporates additional valuable content including metadata from open-access publications in PubMed Central (PMC), pre-review articles and out-of-

¹<https://www.zbmed.de/en/research/current-projects/olspub>

²<https://zenodo.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533303>

³<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁴<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/about/>

scope citations (i.e. publications that fall outside MEDLINE's typical scope but are included for their scientific significance, such as articles of a chemical, physical, or mathematical nature related to biomedicine).

PubMed serves approximately 10 million searches a day to roughly 3 million unique visitors from a variety of backgrounds⁵. Physicians, educators, students, healthcare professionals and industry experts all over the world use PubMed to review research in their areas of interest, track developments and compile literature for systematic reviews.

Many institutions and libraries also **integrate PubMed data into their own platforms**. In addition to prominent examples such as Europe PubMed Central⁶, various other services build upon PubMed data to provide enhanced functionalities and analyses. These include the ZB MED discovery service LIVIVO⁷ as well as Open Alex⁸, Open Knowledge Maps⁹, Semantic Scholar¹⁰, Dimensions¹¹ and many more.

However, the life sciences community – particularly in health and medicine – now faces **real concerns** about PubMed's future. Given recent cuts to science and health programs and increasing political influence from the current US government (Rosenbluth, Teddy; Robbins, Rebecca 2025), researchers fear the following scenarios could materialise:

1. Frequent, prolonged **outages** or the complete discontinuation of PubMed (see McFarling, Usha Lee 2025)
2. Implementation of **usage fees** or geographic limitations restricting PubMed access to US territory (see Incorvaia, Darren 2025).
3. Non-transparent, **politically motivated alterations** to PubMed content or MeSH terms that would compromise the database's scientific integrity (see Tollefson et al. 2025; Waffenschmidt, Siw 2025).

The primary objective of this project is therefore to rapidly establish reliable access to an alternative data source that matches PubMed's comprehensive coverage and functionality. While modifications to the existing PubMed service fall outside our current scope, this initial project will develop an **open-source German/European alternative to PubMed through intensive community collaboration** and establish a sustainable network infrastructure. This will create a resilient foundation for access to medical and life sciences information, providing continuity even in the event of potential restrictions to PubMed access by the US government.

1.2 Existing alternatives to PubMed: advantages and limitations

While PubMed remains a highly respected and widely utilised database for accessing biomedical literature, researchers already have access to **several alternative databases** of scientific publications in the life sciences. While these alternatives offer unique features, they also have certain **limitations when compared to PubMed in terms of comprehensiveness, accessibility and the user experience**.

⁵https://www.nlm.nih.gov/bsd/medline_pubmed_production_stats.html

⁶<https://europepmc.org/About#who-is-behind-europe-pmc>

⁷<https://www.livivo.de>

⁸<https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works>

⁹<https://openknowledgemaps.org/>

¹⁰<https://www.semanticscholar.org/about/publishers>

¹¹<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6579599/>

Embase (Excerpta Medica Database)¹² stands out as an alternative that offers extensive coverage of international scientific literature across medicine, pharmacology and life sciences. Managed by the publisher Elsevier B. V., Embase provides broader European journal coverage and includes extensive conference abstracts. A significant advantage of Embase is its inclusion of articles related to drug research and clinical guidelines. However, unlike PubMed's free access model, Embase requires a subscription fee, creating a significant barrier for many researchers and institutions.

Another alternative is **Scopus**¹³, also maintained by Elsevier B.V., which is renowned for its comprehensive citation indexing. Scopus covers a wide range of scientific disciplines and offers advanced tools for tracking citations and analysing research impact. However, its limitation lies in the fact that it is not specifically focused on life science literature and, like Embase, requires a subscription, certainly limiting access for institutions with restricted funding.

Google Scholar¹⁴ serves as a broadly accessible platform that indexes scholarly articles across numerous disciplines. Its wide coverage and accessibility are commendable, yet Google Scholar lacks the rigorous indexing standards of PubMed. The platform's reliance on automated algorithms can lead to inconsistent citation formats and difficulties in retrieving specific biomedical articles.

Web of Science¹⁵ is another valuable resource offering robust citation analysis tools and a wide breadth of scientific literature. Maintained and managed by Clarivate Analytics, the platform demonstrates particular strengths in indexing highly-cited journals. However, Web of Science does not provide the same depth of life science and medical journal coverage as PubMed and access requires a subscription.

For those looking for cost-free resources, **Europe PMC**¹⁶, **OpenAlex**¹⁷ and **LENS**¹⁸ are viable options. They offer free access to a multitude of bibliographic metadata in life sciences and align closely with the layout and features of PubMed. However, all three databases obtain their data directly from PubMed and are therefore exposed to the same risks described in this proposal. To support our joint vision of facilitating open science, we are in close contact with EMBL-EBI regarding Europe PMC and are working towards collaborative solutions.

In summary, **none of the alternative solutions mentioned here can replace PubMed** and nor can any of the smaller databases that currently exist. Each alternative faces significant limitations: they either depend on PubMed/MEDLINE as their primary data source, cannot deliver equivalent data quality for medical and life sciences research (including lacking subject indexing at the level of MeSH vocabulary and failing to focus specifically on the life sciences domain), or require licensing fees that restrict accessibility.

1.3 ZB MED as a provider of library and discovery service solutions

The "German National Library of Medicine (ZB MED) - Information Centre for Life Sciences" is a foundation that negotiates, licenses and procures comprehensive **life science**

¹²<https://www.embase.com>

¹³<https://www.scopus.com/>

¹⁴<https://scholar.google.com/>

¹⁵<https://www.webofknowledge.com/>

¹⁶<https://europepmc.org>

¹⁷<https://openalex.org/>

¹⁸<https://www.lens.org/>

literature from publishers and scientific institutions, prioritising digital formats with national access¹⁹ in accordance with the foundation's charter²⁰.

For the past decade, ZB MED has offered these resources through the **LIVIVO life science search portal** (Müller et al. 2017), which processed over six million search queries in 2024 alone. LIVIVO aggregates more than 79 million entries from over 40 data sources, making these datasets accessible to other institutions via an application programming interface (API). These **datasets include both PubMed data and German-language literature**, automatically indexed by ZB MED. LIVIVO provides access to over 20 million selected open-access publications, including content from the Repository for Life Sciences (FRL) operated by ZB MED. Publications, theses and conference proceedings in FRL are reliably citable through persistent identifiers (DOI and URN) and benefit from long-term archiving with guaranteed data security. LIVIVO is continuously being developed by ZB MED through own and third-party funded projects²¹.

ZB MED also has experience in developing specialised databases, including the Health-StudyHub²² for research data from clinical, epidemiological and public health studies, as well as the PreVIEW database. Both platforms were efficiently developed in an agile way during the COVID-19 pandemic²³.

Currently, ZB MED is also responsible for **providing and maintaining the German version of MeSH**²⁴. This includes translating MeSH terminology into German and adapting the terms and structures to the German language to ensure that MeSH can be used effectively in German-speaking medical and scientific contexts. Given recent political developments in the US and upcoming changes to the next MeSH edition scheduled for release in November/December 2025, ZB MED will critically evaluate whether these latest modifications follow political influence and may pull the option to follow own judgements and may not adopt all the proposed adjustments.

2 Objectives and Work Programme

2.1 Anticipated total duration of the project

18 months

2.2 Objectives

The main objective of this project is to **enhance the resilience of medical and health research in Germany and beyond by providing access to a stable and reliable instance of the PubMed database**. By taking an open-source approach, we aim to advance Open Science principles while enabling third-party contributions that will strengthen the solution's resilience and adaptability over time. The three key objectives are:

¹⁹<https://www.zbmed.de/en/search-find/overview>

²⁰<https://www.zbmed.de/ueber-uns/profil-zbmed/organisation-und-gesetzestexte/stiftungsgesetz>

²¹<https://www.zbmed.de/en/research/current-projects>

²²<https://www.zbmed.de/en/search-find/german-central-health-study-hub>

²³<https://www.rki.de/DE/Themen/Infektionskrankheiten/Infektionskrankhei.-A-Z/C/COVID-19/Long-COVID/Literaturrecherche.html>

²⁴<https://www.zbmed.de/en/open-science/terminologies/german-mesh>

1. **Data:** Establish the legal and technical frameworks to integrate current publications from publishers, prioritising journal titles currently indexed in PubMed (see 2.3.1 and 2.3.2).
2. **Access:** Build a platform for searching and accessing publications that is similar to the current PubMed interface (see 2.3.4 and 2.3.5) and incorporates MeSH tagging for enhanced search capabilities (see 2.3.3).
3. **Network:** Establish a robust collaborative network of users and enablers – both individuals and institutions – to assist with the long-term development of an open literature database solution for the life sciences and to ensure ongoing European management and organisation of this database (see 2.3.6).

The developed technical solutions will be made available under **open-source** licences and cultivated as community-driven initiatives. This approach ensures seamless knowledge transfer to other teams should national or international restrictions arise in the future.

Community engagement is one of the most important tasks of the project, as an open and resilient infrastructure can only evolve through a sustainable collaborative network (see 2.3.6). We will actively engage scientists, librarians, publishers and developers within Germany, across Europe and worldwide, welcoming contributions from all parties. Four distinct groups will form the core of our community: **(1) end users, including researchers in the life sciences, physicians, information scientists, medical professionals and librarians**, who will actively shape the user experience, **(2) technical enablers, comprising IT developers from medical or infrastructure institutions**, who intend to contribute to the development of database functionalities or integrate data or functions into their services, **(3) publishing partners**, who provide access to their bibliographic metadata (see 2.3.1.3) and **(4) policy-makers and politicians**, who establish the framework for developing resilient research infrastructure.

2.3 Working program and proposed methods

The working program is divided into three sections corresponding to our three key objectives (see figure 1). **Work packages (WP) 1 and 2** focus on the provision of **data and metadata**, including clarifying legal frameworks, negotiating rights with publishers and establishing a technical workflow for delivering the data to a server and integrating it into a search index. **WP 3, 4 and 5** centre on delivering **high-quality access** to data at PubMed-equivalent standards, implementing initial MeSH tagging capabilities for new content and establishing a stable, secure operational environment capable of supporting large-scale user engagement. **WP 6** focuses on community engagement and **network building**, providing quality control mechanisms and gathering requirements that inform all other WPs and future developments.

Aligned with our three objectives and three WP sections, the project will have **three milestones** (MS) tied to three successive database releases: early-alpha, alpha and beta. The **early-alpha version** (MS1, Q2 (quarter), M6 (month)) will prioritise data provision and ensure that **data is available from early on in the project**. This database version will leverage the existing PubMed distribution as a baseline while incorporating additional publisher content secured through ongoing agreements. Core components of this release will include a functional submission portal, initial database infrastructure and preliminary search index, all built upon established PubMed data format standards. The interface will serve exclusively for internal testing and for validating the first configuration of the

discovery system. The **alpha version** will be released to the community, featuring an identical scope of content with **first enhanced access for testing**. This **alpha version** (MS2, Q3, M8) will also provide access to automatically-generated MeSH terms for new publisher content. The **beta version** (MS3, Q5, M15) represents a **full network roll-out** for comprehensive testing and exploration. This milestone will deliver the initial API implementation and a fully-functional search interface, enabling the community to thoroughly evaluate the entire system.

Figure 1: Overview of the OLSPub architecture and stakeholders. Description of the work package can be found in section 2.3

Due to the urgent nature of the situation, the **project duration will be relatively short** (18 months = 6 quarters, three milestones). A total of 9 funded team members (162 person months (PM)), plus an additional 52 PM in-kind, will be involved to **ensure rapid progress** in close collaboration with the community. To enable an **immediate project start** without a hiring phase, we will leverage staff currently working on other third-party funded projects (by reassignments) as well as institutionally funded (in-kind) personnel. Further details are provided in 5.2.

2.3.1 WP 1 -- Administrative and legal framework for data provision

This work package aims to make the same MEDLINE data currently provided by PubMed available in our discovery system at the highest possible level of quality. To achieve this, the first step will involve checking which data are openly accessible and clarifying their associated usage rights (see 2.3.1.1). To extend coverage in addition to freely available data, agreements will then be negotiated with all relevant publishers whose content is already included in MEDLINE (see 2.3.1.2). All rights information will be made available to users in 2.3.1.3 and all communications with publishers will be administered in 2.3.1.4. Rigorous data quality standards will be maintained throughout the process.

2.3.1.1 WP 1.1 – Data from open data sources

This work package involves collecting, registering and securing information rights for all freely available data sources, including CrossRef²⁵, Semantic Scholar²⁶ and existing PubMed data. The search index for milestone 1 is then created on this basis. Currently, up to 90 per cent of bibliographic metadata used in PubMed (as of 2024) is available through CrossRef. However, abstracts, older publications and data from smaller publishers are often absent from CrossRef. Following the success of the Initiative for Open Abstracts²⁷, numerous abstracts are now being made available via CrossRef, with further releases planned. Unfortunately, abstracts from some key life sciences publishers remain unavailable. This project will document and analyse these open sources, making them readily usable for a variety of research projects and for further developments of open science-supporting initiatives. At the same time, their coverage will be compared to that of the current PubMed database. Data sources that are not primarily delivered through PubMed will receive special consideration to promote the integration of open access content.

Deliverable(s): Report summarising data sources used; **Role(s):** Acquisitions Librarian and Librarian; **Resources:** 4 PM DFG, 3 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q3

Figure 2: Gantt chart of the working programme (s. section 2.3)

2.3.1.2 WP 1.2 – Data from proprietary data sources

Agreements are being finalised with the open-access publisher Frontiers. In addition, letters of support will be obtained from SpringerNature, the Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI) and the Company of Biologists, confirming that at least their bibliographic data, including abstracts, will be made available to OLSPub in the same way as it is cur-

²⁵<https://www.crossref.org/>

²⁶<https://www.semanticscholar.org/about>

²⁷<https://i4oa.org/>

rently the case for PubMed and all this for the early-alpha version. Other publishers will be approached through organisations such as the International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers (STM) and via German and international representatives. At the same time, negotiators from library consortia will be contacted and asked to incorporate requests for data provision to OLSPub into their contract negotiations with publishers. A corresponding formulation has already been developed and is already being used by consortia in Sweden, for example.

Deliverable(s): List of agreements (published online); **Role(s):** Acquisitions Librarian and Librarian; **Resources:** 14 PM DFG, 4 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q6

2.3.1.3 WP 1.3 – Provision of rights information for users

The overarching aim of the project is to facilitate re-use and foster future collaboration. To this end, comprehensive information on data usage rights will be systematically gathered, organised and processed. This knowledge will be disseminated through a comprehensive, accessible report targeting end users, librarians, IT developers and other database providers. Information will be updated continuously as sources are integrated. Ultimately, a standardised format for presenting this information will be established, thereby enabling future alternative instances of an open and freely accessible literature infrastructure to benefit from the insights gained in this process. This will make it easier to create similar systems in the future.

Deliverable(s): Report on rights information (Q6); **Role(s):** Librarian; **Resources:** 4 PM DFG, 1 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q4 - Q6

2.3.1.4 WP 1.4 – Publisher communication and data curation

It is expected that communication and transactions with publishers will take place in multiple iterations until stable and accurate data delivery is achieved. This WP, in cooperation with WP 2 (see [2.3.2](#)), will manage these communications and transactions. Support and training sessions will be available for publishers to ensure they understand data submission requirements and can adhere to protocols effectively, thereby streamlining data delivery and minimising potential errors. A protocol for conflict resolution will be established, allowing for the efficient handling of any discrepancies or disagreements regarding data specifications or delivery criteria. This will include defined escalation paths and decision-making authorities within the Data Augmentation Interest Group. Once data delivery agreements are in place, regular verification of delivered data will be essential. A structured verification process will be implemented to ensure that all received data aligns with specified standards and contractual obligations, including the correct inclusion of metadata in our shared metadata format. This process will incorporate automated validation checks using software tools designed to identify discrepancies and ensure data integrity. Unclear cases or variants will be discussed and resolved in consultation with the Data Augmentation Interest Group. Additionally, a feedback mechanism will be established to provide timely updates and address any issues found during the data verification process. This feedback loop will enable continuous improvement in data quality through iterative refinements.

Deliverable(s): Report on standards for data (Q6). **Role(s):** Librarian **Resources:** 14 PM DFG, 4 PM ZB MED **Period:** Q2 - Q6

2.3.2 WP 2 -- Submission service, data ingestion and provision of snapshots

This work package aims to create a **drop-in replacement** for the submission of bibliographic metadata by publishers, as well as for the processing workflows currently provided by the NLM. Its objective is to ensure a seamless transition for metadata providers and data dump users. By providing a technical platform fully compliant with PubMed standards, we seek to facilitate a smooth and efficient migration process, thereby maximising the benefits of our platform. The metadata processing pipeline will offer streamlined ingestion capabilities alongside standardised output formats, creating an essential bridge between legacy systems and the new platform. This approach allows researchers and service providers to take full advantage of our modernised infrastructure while maintaining compatibility with existing tools and practices.

2.3.2.1 WP 2.1 – Submission service

This sub-work package will develop and deliver submission services that are fully compatible with those currently provided by the NLM, allowing data providers (publishers) to upload their metadata, including abstracts, as XML files. The system will support NLM Journal Publishing Tag Set versions 2.3²⁸ and 3²⁹, standards commonly used by publishers when submitting data to the PubMed ingestion pipeline. Additionally, the same FTP server software (ProFTPD³⁰) and procedures will be used to minimise disruptions and reduce overhead for data providers. Ideally, only a simple modification of upload procedures – i.e. changing the FTP URL – will be necessary for providers to connect to the new system. After that, they can continue submitting data without significant changes to their existing workflows.

Deliverable(s): FTP server ready (Q2); **Role(s):** System / DevOps Engineer; **Resources:** 2 PM DFG, 1 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q2

2.3.2.2 WP 2.2 – Data ingestion

This WP will develop a robust metadata pipeline to process PubMed-compatible XML submissions and ingest them into a **centralised database** (PostgreSQL)³¹. The data will follow the **Data Vault 2.0** schema³², enabling a flexible, audit-proof data warehouse with full historical tracking. The open-source tool `datavault4dbt`³³ will be used to full automate raw mart modelling and semi-automate business mart modelling. XML data will be imported directly using PostgreSQL's native XML type and complex transformations will be handled by integrated Python functions (e.g. API queries). An in-database ELT (Extract, Load, Transform) process will ensure optimal performance and consistency. Additionally, Apache AGE³⁴ may be employed for graph-based views, such as references. The resulting business mart will feed both the Solr search index and snapshot exports. The entire workflow will be orchestrated using Apache Airflow³⁵, which supports **parallel processing**.

Deliverable(s): Database (Q1) and workflow management system (Q2) ready; **Role(s):** Data Engineer; **Resources:** 9 PM DFG, 3 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q3

²⁸<https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/nlm-dtd/publishing/2.3/>

²⁹<https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/nlm-dtd/publishing/3.0/>

³⁰<http://www.proftpd.org/>

³¹<https://www.postgresql.org/>

³²<https://datavaultalliance.com/data-vault-2-the-details/>

³³<https://github.com/ScalefreeCOM/datavault4dbt>

³⁴<https://age.apache.org/>

³⁵<https://airflow.apache.org/>

2.3.2.3 WP 2.3 – Provision of snapshots

The new system will be capable of generating **database dumps** that fully comply with the format and specifications currently provided by the NLM³⁶ via an FTP server. It will follow the same frequency with an annual baseline file and daily update files³⁷. All this ensures **full compatibility** with existing tools and workflows that rely on established NLM data standards. By maintaining strict adherence to these widely accepted formats, the system will support a **seamless transition** for users and developers already integrated into the PubMed ecosystem. The snapshot will be openly available for reuse.

Deliverable(s): Automatic snapshot workflow (Q5); **Role(s):** Data Engineer; **Resources:** 2 PM DFG, 1 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q4 - Q5

2.3.3 WP 3 -- Automatic MeSH tagging and metadata enrichment

Keyword-based information retrieval methods can be enriched by adopting semantic approaches that recognise expressions in the text corresponding to ontological terms. While the content and the metadata of the publications form the key elements for any retrieval engine and discovery system, more advanced technologies make use of standardised terminologies and extraction techniques to further improve retrieval (Rebholz-Schuhmann, Pezik, et al. 2008, Rebholz-Schuhmann, Oellrich, and Hoehndorf 2012). NLM has invested considerable effort in developing the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) thesaurus³⁸, a state-of-the-art terminology for the medical domain to capture administrative tasks and by now a wide range of medical topics. PubMed uses MeSH terms to facilitate document indexing and searching³⁹. Initially, the NLM employed a combination of human and automated tagging using the Medical Text Indexer (MTI)⁴⁰; however, since 2022, NLM has moved to an almost entirely automated tagging procedure⁴¹. This project aims to establish a robust automatic tagging system using MeSH terms to deliver document retrieval that meets current NLM standards. Additional sources will be explored to further enrich search and retrieval functionality.

2.3.3.1 WP 3.1 – Implementation of a basic MeSH tagger

Document processing for tagging purposes follows standard procedures such as identification of sentences, single words (tokenisation) and other features (Rebholz-Schuhmann, Oellrich, and Hoehndorf 2012). However, the use of machine learning and deep learning methods can significantly reduce the overhead, provided that a gold standard corpus is available. The research community has invested significant effort in developing such gold standards; however, in the case of PubMed, the repository itself, which includes a large number of documents manually tagged with MeSH terms, constitutes the best gold standard. In fact, PubMed data together with MeSH tagging have been used for more than 10 years in the BioASQ challenge⁴², where one of the primary tasks involves developing automated approaches to assign MeSH terms to PubMed abstracts (Krithara, Mork, et al. 2023; Krithara, Nentidis, et al. 2023). We will train a model using manually tagged documents, either by applying established machine learning techniques – such as Conditional

³⁶https://www.nlm.nih.gov/bsd/licensee/data_elements_doc.html

³⁷<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/download/>

³⁸<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>

³⁹<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/bsd/indexfaq.html>

⁴⁰<https://lhncbc.nlm.nih.gov/ii/tools/MTI.html>

⁴¹https://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/techbull/ma24/ma24_mtix.html

⁴²<https://www.bioasq.org/>

Random Fields, as used in the “MeSH Up” approach (see Trieschnigg et al. 2009) – or by adopting more recent methods such as Large Language Models (LLMs) (Ravinder et al. 2023; You et al. 2020). The results will be added to the abstract metadata, enriching it for use in the search index and ultimately improving retrieval performance and user experience.

Deliverable(s): Annotation pipeline (Q3); **Role(s):** Data Scientist/Software Developer; **Resources:** 9 PM DFG, 3 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1-Q3

2.3.3.2 WP 3.2 – Exploration of alternative tagging approaches

In the second phase of the project, the existing solution will be refined based on feedback from the user community. Several avenues for improvement will be explored, including focusing machine learning methods on specific sentence elements (Gaudan, Kirsch, and Rebholz-Schuhmann 2005), adopting multi-label strategies such as classifier chains (Read et al. 2011), employing active learning techniques and exploiting **scalable deep learning methods**. Hybrid models that apply neural networks in combination with rule-based or ontology-guided constraints can contribute to improving precision and interpretability in specific domains. Lastly, ensemble learning⁴³ will combine outputs from diverse models to achieve robust tagging. This approach will ensure high accuracy and reliability in MeSH term assignment, providing a solid foundation for the proposed PubMed replacement system.

Deliverable(s): Annotation pipeline as part of pilot (Q4), final pipeline (Q6); **Role(s):** Data Scientist/Software Developer; **Resources:** 9 PM DFG, 3 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q4 - Q6

2.3.4 WP 4 -- Search interface

To offer researchers a familiar and user-friendly experience, we will develop a web interface that closely mirrors the functionality of PubMed’s existing platform, as described in its documentation⁴⁴. This new interface will be built on a modern open-source technology stack, ensuring both scalability and maintainability and requires frontend and backend work in a coordinated approach.

2.3.4.1 WP 4.1 – Search index

To enable robust search functionality across our extensive metadata repository, we will integrate **Apache Solr**⁴⁵, a powerful open-source enterprise search platform known for its speed, scalability and advanced query capabilities. Drawing on years of experience operating the LIVIVO search engine, we have developed expertise in field definition, search ranking and the separation of indexing and search tasks. Solr employs **two index types**, kept up to date via replication, minimising the impact on user search performance. Indexing tasks are offloaded from the search servers, ensuring that replication uses only minimal resources. **Load balancing** distributes queries across multiple identical search servers, ensuring performance, reliability and scalability under high demand. Solr’s standard REST interface supports both integration with our web portal and the provision of a public search API.

Deliverable(s): Search Index Solr in pilot (Q1), final version (Q6); **Role(s):** Data Engineer; **Resources:** 7 PM DFG, 2 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q6

⁴³<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/ensemble.html>

⁴⁴<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/help/>

⁴⁵<https://solr.apache.org/>

2.3.4.2 WP 4.2 – Search interface

At its core, the application will be built using Python⁴⁶, known for its versatility and extensive ecosystem of libraries. For handling web requests, we will utilise Quart⁴⁷, a **lightweight, asynchronous Python web framework** that builds upon the strengths of Flask (its predecessor), offering enhanced performance and concurrency capabilities. SwaggerUI⁴⁸ will be used to clearly **define and document the individual endpoints**, ensuring sustainability during development and allowing the community to continue working on the front end, for example. The user interface itself will be crafted in HTML using React.js, a popular JavaScript library renowned for its component-based architecture and ability to create dynamic and responsive web applications.

Deliverable(s): PubMed-style web interface, versions (Q2), (Q3) and (Q5); **Role(s):** Software Developer (Frontend) and Software Developer (Backend); **Resources:** 27 PM DFG, 4 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q6

2.3.4.3 WP 4.3 – Basic API

A basic **API that is compliant with the existing Entrez API specification**⁴⁹ will be implemented to facilitate **programmatic access** to biomedical data in a **machine-readable format**. It will enable researchers and developers to retrieve and manipulate data using standard programming languages and computational tools. The implementation will support the core vocabulary and functionalities defined by the Entrez API. This foundation will ensure interoperability with existing workflows and promote automated data integration and analysis in bioinformatics applications.

Deliverable(s): API for access to data as pilot (Q4) and production version (Q6); **Role(s):** Software Developer (Backend); **Resources:** 9 PM DFG, 3 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q4 - Q6

2.3.5 WP 5 -- Software engineering and service operations

This work package will follow established software engineering best practices and adopt an Infrastructure-as-Code approach to deliver high-quality software, thereby laying solid foundations for the community to extend and build upon our solutions.

2.3.5.1 WP 5.1 – Software development standards

This project will apply established software engineering practices to ensure a maintainable and efficient development process which will be documented in a development strategy and guideline document. We will use **Git-based version control** with logical branching and a clear project history. A **Behavior-Driven Development (BDD)**-based approach will be established to align code with user expectations. Robust **testing** – including unit, integration and system tests – will ensure code reliability. **CI/CD** pipelines will be implemented using GitLab Runners to automate integration and delivery. Code quality will be enforced through **linters**, style guides and **peer reviews**. Clear **documentation** will be generated early on and maintained throughout the project. **Security** will be integrated from the start. Following **agile principles**, work will be managed via **Kanban boards** with a hierarchical task structure which will be set up for this purpose.

Deliverable(s): Guideline document (Q1); **Role(s):** all technical roles; **Resources:** 1 PM DFG, 1 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q6

⁴⁶<https://www.python.org/>

⁴⁷<https://quart.palletsprojects.com>

⁴⁸<https://swagger.io/tools/swagger-ui/>

⁴⁹<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK25501/>

2.3.5.2 WP 5.2 – DevOps

The development and deployment of this platform will follow the **DevOps philosophy** and **Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC)** approach, ensuring seamless automation and efficient management throughout its lifecycle. Server setup and maintenance will be fully automated using **Ansible**⁵⁰ and **Docker**⁵¹, two industry-standard open-source technologies. This approach not only streamlines deployment but also enhances consistency and reliability across all infrastructure components. The complete set of configuration scripts and container images will be made openly accessible to the community, fostering collaboration and transparency (on GitHub⁵² and Codeberg⁵³ with release snapshots on Zenodo⁵⁴). The entire system will be hosted on compute infrastructure supplied by the **German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI)**⁵⁵. de.NBI is a national, academic and non-profit infrastructure supported by the German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTB). It provides bioinformatics services to users in life sciences research and biomedicine across Germany and Europe. As outlined in a letter of commitment, de.NBI has pledged to provide the necessary resources. The commitment from de.NBI ensures that the project will have the robust infrastructure needed to support its objectives and deliver reliable performance. Additionally, this setup can be scaled to accommodate changing needs, providing flexibility and supporting future growth as requirements evolve. **Deliverable(s)**: Report on infrastructure as code (Basic (Q3), Production (Q6)); **Role(s)**: System / DevOps Engineer; **Resources**: 6 PM DFG, 2 PM ZB MED; **Period**: Q1 - Q6

2.3.5.3 WP 5.3 – Platform operation

To ensure robust security, optimal performance and comprehensive observability, the platform will employ a **multi-layered strategy** throughout its development and operation. A **reverse proxy** will be set up to handle HTTPS encryption, filter bots, mitigate DoS attacks and perform **load balancing** across backend services, including Solr if needed. **Client-side CAPTCHA**, using tools such as Anubis⁵⁶, will be integrated to protect against AI-driven crawlers. A **Matomo** instance will be hosted to track visitor data such as geolocation and behaviour. Logs from both the backend and proxy will be processed through a **self-hosted ELK stack**⁵⁷ (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana) to support **proactive bot detection** and inform scaling decisions. To maintain search engine visibility, an SEO pipeline will be set up to auto-generate and regularly submit XML sitemaps that reflect dynamic content changes.

Deliverable(s): Proxy server (Q2), logs available (Q3), provenance in public search engines (Q4); **Role(s)**: A) System / DevOps Engineer B) Software Developer (backend); **Resources**: 9 PM DFG, 2 PM ZB MED; **Period**: Q2 - Q6

2.3.6 WP 6 -- Sustainable network

To ensure the project is developed in line with user group needs over the long term, we consider it essential to build a community that supports us by formulating requirements

⁵⁰<https://docs.ansible.com/>

⁵¹<https://www.docker.com/>

⁵²<https://github.com/>

⁵³<https://codeberg.org/>

⁵⁴<https://zenodo.org/>

⁵⁵<https://www.denbi.de/>

⁵⁶<https://anubis.techaro.lol>

⁵⁷<https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack>

and providing feedback. This WP will establish communication with diverse communities (end users, IT developers, decision-makers; see 2.2), enabling their targeted involvement in alpha and beta testing (see 2.3.6.1) and integrating their contribution to planning the platform's continued operation and future development (see 2.3.6.2).

2.3.6.1 WP 6.1 Communication and quality control

Our communication strategy is designed to reach a broad interested audience, from which focused interest groups will be formed for in-depth testing and feedback. Continuous quality control will gather early feedback on the three main development areas: enriched data (including automatic MeSH tagging), IT solution capabilities and user interface functionality. Following the initial internal testing of an early-alpha version in late Q2 (milestone 1), the alpha version will be released in Q3 (milestone 2) with testing of the **search interface** by end users. A subsequent **open testing phase** will invite the broader web user community, alongside interest groups, to evaluate functionalities until the beta version release at the end of Q5 (milestone 3). Test scenarios for this open phase will be implemented in the form of a survey. **End users** will be engaged via the ZB MED blog, social networks and mailing lists. We will also host monthly “ask me anything” sessions, offer workshops on demand and make presentations at established conferences such as AGMB, SWIB, EAHIL and IFLA, as well as at events organised by initiatives such as the National Research Data Infrastructure including (e.g. NFDI4Health, NFDI4Microbiota). **MeSH tagging** will be monitored by **librarians** from the alpha version release onwards. This group will also monitor any further developments in the MeSH thesaurus. The **IT developers** interest group will focus on the **technical set-up** and will provide continuous feedback and suggestions for improvement, independent of the version release schedule. After an initial phase in Q1, monthly meetings will be held to report on the current status and collect targeted feedback, enabling OLSPub integration with other services. The frequency of regular meetings and additional networking events will be adjusted based on community needs. We will also organise dedicated community events for **political decision-makers** to raise awareness of the importance of resilient research infrastructures. This will be required at national and European levels and will include roundtable discussions and invitations to present at conferences.

Deliverable(s): Reports on test results (Q3) and survey results (Q6); **Role(s):** Community Manager (technical background) and Community Manager (life science background); **Resources:** 18 PM DFG, 5 PM ZB MED; **Period:** Q1 - Q6

2.3.6.2 WP 6.2 Future work, resilient infrastructure and potential spin-off projects

This WP will develop a comprehensive roadmap to ensure a resilient and sustainable infrastructure in the long term, working closely with national and international partners and involving organisations such as the NLM and EMBL-EBI whenever possible. An agreement is already in place with EMBL-EBI (see Letter of Support) to pursue future collaboration. This partnership will be strengthened throughout the project through regular quarterly meetings, aligned with our commitment to open infrastructure principles. The planning process will incorporate **user community feedback** (see 2.3.6.1) and culminate in a future plan in Q5, which will be made publicly available. We anticipate various priorities for further development, such as enhancing the search interface, extending coverage to PubMed Central (including full-text articles), integrating additional databases such as AGRICOLA⁵⁸ and implementing technical innovations – for example, adopting federated or distributed

⁵⁸<https://www.nal.usda.gov/agricola>

architectures and peer-to-peer distribution mechanisms to increase resilience. In addition, the future plan will identify opportunities for **new funding proposals** and potential **spin-off projects**. **Deliverable(s)**: Future work plan (Q5); **Role(s)**: Community Manager (technical background) **Resources**: 18 PM DFG, 1 PM ZB MED; **Period**: Q3 - Q6

2.3.7 WP 7 -- Project management and administration

This WP will establish a project management framework to coordinate all other WPs and keep activities aligned with project goals. Management responsibilities will be shared between the “Discovery Services” division of the “Data Science and Services” unit (lead) and the “ZB MED Library” unit. Weekly coordination meetings will address challenges and synchronise tasks across WPs. Project tracking will utilise GitLab for version-controlled document sharing, task assignment, milestone tracking and issue management, supporting effective collaboration, transparency and access to current resources. The project management team will also monitor overall progress, ensure adherence to timelines and DFG compliance and prepare and write regular reports.

Deliverable(s): Gitlab setup (Q1), midterm report (Q3), final report (Q6); **Role(s)**: Senior Mangement Staff (IT, Library); **Resources**: 0 PM DFG, 9 PM ZB MED; **Period**: Q1 - Q6

3 Project- and subject-related list of publications

- Gaudan, Sylvain, Harald Kirsch, and Dietrich Rebholz-Schuhmann (2005). “Resolving abbreviations to their senses in Medline”. In: *Bioinformatics* 21.18, pp. 3658–3664.
- Incorvaia, Darren (Apr. 8, 2025). *NIH blocks researchers in China, Russia and other countries from multiple databases*.
- Krithara, Anastasia, James G. Mork, Anastasios Nentidis, and Georgios Paliouras (Sept. 2023). “The road from manual to automatic semantic indexing of biomedical literature: a 10 years journey”. English. In: *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics* 8. Publisher: Frontiers.
- Krithara, Anastasia, Anastasios Nentidis, Konstantinos Bougiatiotis, and Georgios Paliouras (Mar. 2023). “BioASQ-QA: A manually curated corpus for Biomedical Question Answering”. In: *Scientific Data* 10.1, p. 170.
- McFarling, Usha Lee (Apr. 24, 2025). *Day by day, how Trump is roiling science and health*.
- Müller, Bernd, Christoph Poley, Jana Pössel, Alexandra Hagelstein, and Thomas Gubitza (Mar. 2017). “LIVIVO – the Vertical Search Engine for Life Sciences”. In: *Datenbank-Spektrum* 17.1, pp. 29–34.
- Ravinder, Rohitha, Tim Fellerhoff, Vishnu Dadi, Lukas Geist, Guillermo Rocamora, Muhammad Talha, Dietrich Rebholz-Schuhmann, and Leyla Jael Castro (2023). “OntoClue, a framework to compare vector-based approaches for document relatedness using the RELISH corpus”. In: *Proceedings Semantic Web Applications and Tools for Healthcare and Life Sciences, February 13–16, 2023, Basel, Switzerland*. RWTH Aachen, pp. 159–160.
- Read, Jesse, Bernhard Pfahringer, Geoff Holmes, and Eibe Frank (Dec. 2011). “Classifier chains for multi-label classification”. In: *Machine Learning* 85.3, pp. 333–359.
- Rebholz-Schuhmann, Dietrich, Anika Oellrich, and Robert Hoehndorf (2012). “Text-mining solutions for biomedical research: enabling integrative biology”. In: *Nature Reviews Genetics* 13.12, pp. 829–839.
- Rebholz-Schuhmann, Dietrich, Piotr Pezik, et al. (2008). “Biolexicon: Towards a reference terminological resource in the biomedical domain”. In: *6th Annual International Conference on Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology (ISMB-2008)*.
- Richter-Kuhlmann, Eva (Apr. 2025). “Momentan müssen wir uns jederzeit auf drastische Einschränkungen gefasst machen”. In: *Deutsches Ärzteblatt*.
- Rosenbluth, Teddy; Robbins, Rebecca (Apr. 2025). “Trump-Allied Prosecutor Sends Letters to Medical Journals Alleging Bias”. In: *The New York Times*.
- Tollefson, Jeff, Dan Gristo, Max Kozlov, and Alexandra Witze (May 2025). “NIH under siege”. English. In: *Science* 388 (6747). Publisher: American Association for the Advancement of Science, pp. 578–580.
- Trieschnigg, Dolf, Piotr Pezik, Vicky Lee, Franciska de Jong, Wessel Kraaij, and Dietrich Rebholz-Schuhmann (June 2009). “MeSH Up: effective MeSH text classification for improved document retrieval”. In: *Bioinformatics* 25.11, pp. 1412–1418.
- Waffenschmidt, Siw (Mar. 26, 2025). *What to do if PubMed goes down the drain*.
- You, Ronghui, Yuxuan Liu, Hiroshi Mamitsuka, and Shanfeng Zhu (Sept. 2020). “BERTMeSH: deep contextual representation learning for large-scale high-performance MeSH indexing with full text”. In: *Bioinformatics* 37.5, pp. 684–692. eprint: <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article-pdf/37/5/684/50356276/btaa837.pdf>.